

The Covid- 19 Pandemic and Sexual Violence against Women: A Spacial and Temporal Analysis of Rapes in Pernambuco, Brazil

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RESUMO

A violência sexual e o estupro são ataques ao corpo e à dignidade de uma mulher; tais agressões têm consequências psicológicas, sociais e econômicas para o resto de sua vida. A pandemia pela COVID-19 expôs e exacerbou as desigualdades dentro dos países, com a maior vulnerabilidade das mulheres a violência doméstica, sexual e feminicídios. Este estudo objetivou analisar a tendência temporal das taxas de estupro contra as mulheres em Pernambuco, no período pré-pandêmico e pandêmico. Foram registrados 8.948 estupros contra as mulheres no período, com 5.076 (56,7%) ocorridos no pré-pandêmico. No período pandêmico observou-se redução nas taxas de estupro contra as mulheres na população adulta e na Região Metropolitana. As reduções na taxa de estupro contra as mulheres encontradas, podem refletir a subnotificação na pandemia, além do estigma, medo, vergonha e culpabilização das vítimas.

Palavras-chave: violência contra as mulheres; estupro; Covid-19; análise espacial; análise de séries temporais interrompida.

ABSTRACT

Sexual violence and rape are attacks on a woman's body and dignity; such assaults have psychological, social and economic consequences for the rest of her life. The COVID-19 pandemic has exposed and exacerbated inequalities within countries, with women being more vulnerable to domestic and sexual violence and femicides. This study aimed to analyze the

temporal trend of rape rates against women in Pernambuco, in the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods. There were 8,948 rapes against women in the period, with 5,076 (56.7%) occurring in the pre-pandemic. In the pandemic period, there was a reduction in rape rates against women in the adult population and in the Metropolitan Region. The reductions in the rate of rape against women found may reflect underreporting during the pandemic, as well as stigma, fear, shame and victim-blaming.

Keywords: violence against women; rape; COVID-19; spatial analysis; interrupted time series analysis.

1 INTRODUCTION

Violence against women is a serious social problem and the most prevalent form of human rights violation. Globally, it is estimated that one in three women has experienced physical and/or sexual violence from an intimate partner or sexual violence from any perpetrator during their lifetime (WHO, 2020a). Violence against women is known to increase during humanitarian crises, conflicts, natural disasters, and epidemics (Onyango et al., 2019; Mittal; Singh, 2020; Thurston; Stöckl; Ranganathan, 2021), and this violence is estimated to have increased by 20% during the COVID-19 pandemic (WHO, 2020b).

In these extreme situations, pre-existing gender inequalities and power hierarchies are intensified, consequently increasing cases of sexual violence (Dosdale; Skarparis, 2020). While sexual violence is fundamentally related to power and control, this type of violence can intensify when the perpetrator experiences personal insecurity regarding employment, finances, and/or social life, (Dosdale; Skarparis, 2020).

Among the forms of violence against women, this study highlights sexual violence, specifically rape, which has devastating effects on adult and child victims, their families, and communities. In addition, there are extensive immediate and long-term consequences for the physical and mental health of survivors (Oram; Khalifeh; Howard, 2017; Grose et al., 2021). Victims are exposed to reproductive tract infections, the risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), emotional problems, and the risk of unwanted pregnancy (Grose et al., 2021).

According to the World Health Organization (2013), sexual violence includes acts ranging from verbal abuse to forced penetration and various forms of coercion, from social pressure to intimidation and physical force. Rape is sexual violence that compromises the physical and social well-being of the victim. This violence generally occurs in the domestic environment, making reporting difficult due to the fear imposed on victims, leading to the perpetuation of violence as a result of the patriarchal culture (Vidal e Alves, 2020).

The search for knowledge about reported cases of sexual violence against women during the pandemic can contribute to preventing and addressing this violence, and giving greater visibility to the problem. Therefore, this study aimed to analyze the temporal trend of rape rates against women in the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods in the state of Pernambuco.

1.1 VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN AND THE BRAZILIAN LEGISLATION

In 1994, due to the significant number of cases of violence suffered by women, the Organization of American States brought together several countries, including Brazil, to discuss this issue. This meeting was called the Belém do Pará Convention and Brazil committed to preventing and punishing gender-based violence (Bandeira; Almeida, 2015).

In 1998, sexual violence was widely discussed in Brazil, and in 1999 the Ministry of Health implemented the first technical standard for the care of victims of sexual violence. The aim was to provide comprehensive care to these victims through prevention and treatment of this problem. As most victims were women, the standard was the care for this gender and adolescents (Lima; Larocca; Nascimento, 2019).

With the creation of the Special Secretariat for Policies for Women (Portuguese acronym: SPM) through Law 10.683 in 2003, public policies were established to improve the lives of Brazilian women. The purpose was to eradicate all forms of inequality affecting women. This secretariat had ministerial status and was linked to the Presidency of the Republic, and services such as Reference Centers, Women's Advocates, and Support Networks were created (Bigliardi; Antunes; Wanderbroocke, 2016).

In 2004, due to feminist movements that pressured the government, Bill No. 4.559/2004 was drafted, establishing mechanisms to prevent domestic and family violence against women, which led to Law No. 11.340/2006 - the Maria da Penha Law. Prior to this, there was no comprehensive legislation on domestic and family violence that included protective and preventive measures for women (Morera et al., 2014). The National Plan of Policies for Women and the National Policy to Combat Violence against Women were also established, seeking strategies for preventing and combating violence against women, as well as supporting and guaranteeing their rights (Brazil, 2011). Examples include referral centers for women, shelter services, public defender offices, health services, and forensic medical centers (Brazil, 2011).

According to the Maria da Penha Law, sexual violence occurs when a woman is forced to participate in, witness, or maintain sexual relations without her consent, including domestic violence when she is prevented from deciding whether or not to have children; is prohibited from using any contraceptive method; is forced to have sexual relations against her will, while ill or asleep; forcing acts that cause discomfort, whether the aggressor has a family relationship or not, including those sporadically involved, whether within the family, understood as individuals who are or are not considered relatives, or in any intimate relationship of affection, living with the victim or not, regardless of cohabitation (Brazil, 2013).

Actions to provide protection, access, and prevent this harm to women have emerged, such as the National Plan of Policies for Women, the National Policy to Combat Violence Against Women, specialized police stations for women (DEAM), the National Pact to Combat Violence Against Women, and the Maria da Penha Law (Brazil, 2011).

The National Pact to Combat Violence Against Women is a federative agreement between the federal government and state and municipal governments with actions for the implementation of integrated public policies throughout the national territory. The proposal has five structuring axes: the applicability of the Maria da Penha Law, strengthening service networks and their implementation, access to justice, and guarantee of security, sexual and reproductive rights with combating sexual exploitation, and guaranteeing autonomy with the expansion of women's rights (Brazil, 2011).

All these achievements were important for guaranteeing women's rights to security and health during the period of social distancing and isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the possibility of seeking help has decreased in that period, and this situation may have worsened for women living with their abuser, increasing the likelihood of suffering any type of violence and not having the support of friends and/or family (Marques et al., 2020).

1.2 SEXUAL VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN: REFLECTION OF THE CONTEXT OF GENDER INEQUALITIES

Violence against women is not a recent phenomenon. Patriarchalism has led society to dictate aggressive behavior for men and gentle, submissive behavior for women. This behavior, maintained and reproduced socially, has strengthened the domination of men over women through physical and psychological force (Brazil, 2018; Passos; Gomes; Gonçalves, 2018).

The structural subordination dictated by patriarchy fosters situations of familial violence, a pattern reinforced by the way women are socialized, toward the desires of others rather than their own. This allows for the emergence of threats, emotional influence, and even violence without occurrence of any resistance (Machado; Castanheira; Almeida, 2021).

Women have been placed in inferior positions to men, generating inequalities in social standing and consequently reinforcing the idea of male power over women, including over their bodies, favoring abuse and consequently violence (Martinelli, 2020). Society approves of obedient and demure women, and considers vulgar those who express their sexual desire. However, the same behavior shown by men is not condemned, and this stems from a patriarchal culture. Based on this, women become objects of desire at the disposal of men to satisfy their sexual needs, regardless of women's consent (Vidal; Alves, 2020).

Sexual violence against women has been frequent throughout history with victims often blaming themselves for what happened. Society in general ends up naturalizing this violence, which depends on the sociocultural contexts in which it occurs (Roque, 2018). Women who are victims of sexual violence are also more likely to develop problems in their sexual, romantic, and professional lives, as they become more vulnerable and less secure, which this leads them to develop harmful feelings that favor depression. Buchbinder et al. (2021) observed that 76% of women who sought emergency care after experiencing sexual violence had post-traumatic stress, depression, or anxiety.

Globally, it is estimated that 31% of women between the ages of 15 and 49 years have experienced physical and/or sexual violence by a male intimate partner or sexual violence by a non-partner (strangers, acquaintances, friends, colleagues, teachers, neighbors, family members), or both forms of violence combined. This means that since the age of 15, these women have been victims of at least one form. Overall, physical and sexual violence by an intimate partner and sexual violence by a non-partner remains widespread in the lives of women and girls worldwide.

Although research analyzing the temporal trend of sexual violence in 195 countries and territories between 1990 and 2017 showed a reduction, it does not appear to be considerable. Furthermore, in countries with a low Human Development Index (HDI), sexual violence against women showed an increasing trend (Borumandnia et al., 2020).

In Brazil, the 2019 National Health Survey included a specific module on the experience of violence. Interviews were conducted with people aged 18 or older in nearly 100,000 permanent private households. Of the total, 46,869 were women, and 8.9% reported having suffered some type of sexual violence in their lives (IBGE, 2021). When the survey considered only the 12 months prior to the survey, 1.2 million people were victims of sexual violence. Of this total, 885,000 were women, representing 72.7%, and intimate partners or ex-partners were responsible for the sexual assaults in 53.3% of the cases.

1.3 SEXUAL VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN AND THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The pandemic had an immense impact on violence against women and girls, who face multiple forms of discrimination, and it was considered by the UN as the dark pandemic of violence against women (Mukhtar; Mukhtar; Rana, 2021). According to Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, Director-General of the WHO, violence against women is endemic in all countries and cultures, and the COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated this situation.

With the measures imposed by social distancing, women victims of violence were confined to their homes with their abusers and distant from people who could provide them with help. This facilitated the occurrence of violence, a situation that can foster various types of violence, including rape (Mazza et al., 2020).

Initial reports on the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the concern of organizations protecting women victims of violence regarding the intensification of violence (Roesch et al., 2020). The United Nations Population Fund predicted a 20% increase in domestic and sexual violence during the pandemic (United Nations Population Fund, 2020). According to Okur (2016), sexual violence increases in crisis situations due to violations of the law, and victims often do not receive adequate support while perpetrators go unpunished.

In an online survey of 15,000 Australian women conducted during the early stages of the COVID-19 pandemic, 4.6% of respondents experienced physical and/or sexual violence from a current or former intimate partner with whom they cohabited. The violence began or increased during the pandemic, and many women reported that they did not seek help due to concerns for their security (Boxall; Morgan; Brown, 2020).

In Kenya, women are admittedly more vulnerable to sexual and physical violence at all times of the day in attacks from both strangers and known assailants (e.g., intimate partners) occurring in both private residences and public spaces. Due to social isolation and confinement in enclosed environments with abusers, reports of sexual abuse have become more frequent (Flowe et al., 2020).

A study analyzing 48 rape cases in Nigeria during the pandemic found that 12.5% resulted in femicide. Furthermore, there was a 5.1% increase in March and a 33.3% increase in June 2020 (Owonikoko; Momodu; Suleiman, 2023).

In Brazil, according to the third edition of the “Visível e Invisível” (“Visible and Invisible”) research report on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on the victimization of women, around 3.7 million Brazilian women (5.4%) suffered sexual assault or forced sexual attempts in 2021 (Brazilian Forum on Public Security, 2021).

In fact, the COVID-19 pandemic not only led to an increase in cases of gender-based violence, but also separated women from their social support networks. To reduce the prevalence of violence, it is essential to recognize its extent and strengthen government policies and intersectoral support networks to facilitate victims’ access in the pandemic and post-pandemic context (Ferreira Cortes et al., 2020; Mittal; Singh, 2020).

The intensification of violence against women during the COVID-19 pandemic may have compromised the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) target number 5, which is to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls (United Nations, 2023).

2 METHODOLOGICAL STRATEGIES

This is an ecological study conducted in Pernambuco (Figure 1). The state has a territorial extension of 98,312 km², 184 municipalities and the state district of Fernando de Noronha distributed across five mesoregions: Agreste (71 municipalities), São Francisco (15 municipalities), Sertão (41 municipalities), Recife Metropolitan Region (15 municipalities), and Zona da Mata (43 municipalities). The estimated population for the year 2021 was 9,705,888 inhabitants, of which 5,014,300 (51.6%) were female.

The data on rape cases against women were sourced from microdata in the information system of the Pernambuco State Secretariat of Social Defense (Portuguese acronym: SDS/PE), made publicly available every month since 2015. Rape is defined by the SDS/PE as sexual assault, generally involving sexual intercourse or other forms of lewd acts committed against a person without their consent, according to articles 213 and 217-A of the penal code (Pernambuco, 2022).

Figure 1 – Regionalization diagram of the state of Pernambuco by mesoregion.

Descriptive statistics of the total number of rapes against women were initially calculated according to age groups (up to 17 years; 18 to 34 years; 35 years or more) and mesoregion. Although the geopolitical division of the state is composed of five mesoregions, for the actions of the public security plan, data from the Sertão and Sertão do São Francisco mesoregions are compiled jointly by the SDS/PE (Figure 1). These mesoregions have geographical, climatological, social, economic, and cultural similarities that justify their aggregated analysis.

A regression model was applied using the following explanatory variables: time in months; and a variable indicating the period before COVID-19 and after COVID-19. The Gamma regression model was used for data analysis, because the variable under analysis is a strictly positive variable with an asymmetrical distribution (Paula, 2004).

The model was initially estimated considering the interaction between time and the variable indicating the pre-COVID-19 pandemic period (2018-2019) and the pandemic period (2020-2021). This model underwent a stepwise variable selection process using the Generalized Akaike Information Criteria (GAIC) metric. The R programming language, version 4.1.2, was used to perform all calculations and graphs. The significance level of the study was set at 5%. The models were estimated using the GAMLSS package, version 5.3.4.

The rape rate against women used the estimate of the female population provided by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics and was calculated for two periods of the COVID-19 pandemic: pre-pandemic and pandemic.

This rate is given by the following equation:

$$TxE = \frac{TEcM}{PMi} 100.000 \quad (1)$$

where TxE = rape rate; TEcM = total number of rapes against women; PM = female population; i = reference period.

Note that population estimates are available year by year, and the COVID-19 pandemic period began with the first case registered in the state in March 2020. Furthermore, as the periods total two years, the data normalization to compose the rate was done using the 2019 female population estimate (the period before COVID-19) and the 2021 estimate (the pandemic period).

For spatial distribution, maps showing the distribution of rates in the pre-pandemic and pandemic periods were created. The shapefiles were obtained from the geobr package, version 1.7.0 (Pereira, 2022). In the thematic maps, the rates were stratified using the quartile method. In the stratification performed, the quartile values were fixed considering the period before COVID-19 for comparison purposes.

As secondary publicly available data were used in this study without identifying the subjects, evaluation by the Research Ethics Committee is not necessary.

3 RESULTS

A total of 8,948 rape cases against women were recorded during the analyzed period; 5,076 (56.7%) occurred before the pandemic and 3,872 (43.3%) during the COVID-19 pandemic. The total number of rapes by age group was as follows: 6,439 (72%) occurred in the age group up to 17 years; 1,743 (19.5%) in the age group 18-34 years; and 766 (8.6%) in the age group of 35 years or older.

The average rate (\pm SD) during the period was 4.6 (\pm 0.6) for those up to 17 years old; 1.16 (\pm 0.23) for those aged 18-34 years; and 0.451 (\pm 0.14) for those aged 35 or older. Analysis of rapes by age group and model estimates for rape rate per 100,000 women (Table 1 and Table 2) showed a reduction in the 18-34 age group; the average was 1.27 before the pandemic and 1.04 during the COVID-19 pandemic, representing a 17.9% decrease. For ages 35 and older, the rate also decreased, with an average of 0.50 before COVID-19 and 0.39 after COVID-19, a 21.2% decrease. This decrease was not observed in the under-17 age group, as, according to the applied model, there was no statistically significant reduction between the analyzed periods.

The results demonstrated a decrease in the rape rate against women in the adult population and in the Recife Metropolitan Region. In Brazil, during the pandemic period, there was a reduction in the number of reported cases of sexual violence (Bohnenberger; Bueno, 2021). However, this should be analyzed with great caution, since a reduction in reported cases of sexual violence does not necessarily represent a decrease in its occurrence. Sexual crimes have a well-known high rate of underreporting (Bohnenberger; Bueno, 2021). In research analyzing the underreporting of violence against women in Brazil and its states, a rate of 89.4% for sexual violence was identified, and this rate was 87.3% for the state of Pernambuco (Vasconcelos et al., 2024).

Regarding the rape rate, a decrease was observed in the age groups of 18-34 years and 35 years or older during the pandemic period. This result may be associated with underreporting that this period may have generated, due to women's limitations in accessing public services such as police, justice, and social services (John et al., 2021). Sexual violence is an event that is already underreported, and during emergencies, natural disasters, and pandemics, it is more difficult to report and document (Rockowitz et al., 2021). The social myth surrounding rape—which incorrectly frames assailants as strangers—is reinforced by the fact that most sexual assaults involve someone known to the victim, contributing to increased underreporting (Madeiro et al., 2019).

Table 1 – Descriptive statistics of rape rates against women (per 100,000) by age group, Pernambuco, 2018-2021.

Variable	Period	Age range (in years)	Minimum	Median	Median	Maximum	Standard deviation
Rape rate per 100,000 women	Pre-pandemic	Up to 17	3.69	4.69	4.70	5.53	0.48
		18-34	0.83	1.25	1.27	1.67	0.20
		35 or older	0.23	0.51	0.50	0.79	0.15
	Pandemic	Up to 17	3.24	4.44	4.48	6.13	0.71
		18-34	0.58	1.07	1.04	1.41	0.20
		35 or older	0.16	0.39	0.39	0.58	0.11

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Table 2 – Gamma regression model estimates for the rape rate per 100,000 women, Pernambuco, 2018-2021.

Age range			
Coefficient		Estimate	p-value
Up to 17 years old	Intercept	1.526	0.000
	Dispersion parameter	-2.035	0.000
18-34 years old	Intercept	0.237	0.000
	Pandemic period	-0.197	0.000
	Dispersion parameter	-1.727	0.000
35 years old or older	Intercept	-0.695	0.000
	Pandemic period	-0.239	0.007
	Dispersion parameter	-1.229	0.000
Mesoregion			
Coefficient		Estimate	p-value
Recife Metropolitan Region	Intercept	0.813	0.000
	Pandemic period	-0.228	0.000
	Dispersion parameter	-1.897	0.000
Agreste	Intercept	0.623	0.000
	Dispersion parameter	-1.691	0.000
Sertão	Intercept	0.767	0.000
	Time	-0.007	0.170
	Pandemic period	-0.340	0.201
	Time * Pandemic	0.012	0.143
	Dispersion parameter	-1.632	0.000
Zona da Mata	Intercept	0.608	0.000
	Dispersion parameter	-1.373	0.000

Source: Prepared by the authors.

In Pará, research on rapes conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic also observed a reduction in reported cases. This is explained by the underreporting of rapes, given the silence of the victim. It is understood that rape occurs “under a silent aura, camouflaged by normality”, in broad daylight and committed by people close to the victim (Santos Júnior; Ramos; Almeida, 2023).

As women spent more time with the abuser, the likelihood of violence increased. Aggressors took advantage of isolation measures to impose their power and abuse women in a situation of disadvantage, lacking contact with anyone to obtain help and often without access to means of communication (Nigam, 2020).

The investigation of violence and sexual abuse became more difficult for healthcare professionals during the period of social isolation due to reduced access to health services, staff reassignment, and reduced staff numbers resulting from social isolation and distancing rules. Given that health services and other support services, including sexual and reproductive health services, were reduced, women victims of violence may have had fewer opportunities to receive support and referrals from the health sector (Dosdale; Skarparis, 2020).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, reports to authorities of rape and serious sexual offenses decreased in several locations, while calls to domestic violence helplines increased (Spence et al., 2022). In Italy, although a considerable reduction in calls to these helplines was observed, the number of desperate text messages and emails sent to these organizations increased. Many victims were afraid of being overheard by their abusive partners or prevented from leaving home, and therefore used text messages and email to ask for help (Graham-Harrison et al., 2020).

In Bangladesh, a report analyzing sexual violence against women from January to December 2020 identified that at least 975 women were raped, 204 were victims of attempted rape, and 43 women died after being raped (ASK, 2020).

In New Delhi, the capital of India, around 2,500 calls were made by women to the emergency helpline during social isolation, of which 600 calls were classified as abuse of women and 23 were due to rape (Das; Das; Mandal, 2020). In some quarantine centers in India, cases of rape and sexual assault occurred (Vranda; Febna, 2020).

Analysis of the distribution of rapes by mesoregion showed a concentration of cases in the Recife Metropolitan Region with 3,937 (44%); followed by the Agreste region, with 2,166 (24.2%). The Sertão/São Francisco (n = 1603; 17.9%) and Zona da Mata (n = 1242; 13.9%) mesoregions had the lowest number of registered cases. The average rate (\pm SD) per region was 2.04 (\pm 0.38) for the Recife Metropolitan Region; 1.86 (\pm 0.33) for the Agreste region; 1.92 (\pm 0.39) for the Sertão/São Francisco region; and 1.84 (\pm 0.44) for the Zona da Mata region.

Estimates from the models and the average rape rate per 100,000 women (Table 2 and Table 3) showed that the Metropolitan Region was the only one that demonstrated a reduction: in the pre-pandemic period, the average rape rate was 2.26 per 100,000 women; and during the pandemic period it was 1.79 per 100,000, demonstrating a decrease of 20.4%. The Agreste, Sertão, and Zona da Mata regions showed statistical stability between these two periods.

Table 3 – Descriptive statistics of rape rates against women (per 100,000) by mesoregion, Pernambuco, 2018-2021

Variable	Period	Mesoregion	Minimum	Median	Mean	Maximum	SD
Rape rate per 100,000	Pre-pandemic	RMR	1.77	2.30	2.26	2.92	0.29
		Agreste	0.96	1.86	1.85	2.49	0.34

women		Sertão	1.09	1.97	1.96	2.96	0.40
		Zona da Mata	1.29	1.96	1.91	2.99	0.41
	Pandemic	RMR	1.23	1.73	1.79	2.54	0.33
		Agreste	1.19	1.87	1.89	2.46	0.32
		Sertão	1.19	1.85	1.87	2.78	0.39
		Zona da Mata	0.63	1.80	1.75	2.61	0.47

Source: Prepared by the authors.

SD = Standard Deviation; RMR = Recife Metropolitan Region

In terms of spatial distribution, rape rates against women in the pre-pandemic period (Figure 2a) were widespread throughout the state, without apparent concentration in any particular region. Regarding the pandemic period, a concentration was observed in the eastern and western regions, although without a clear clustering (Figure 2b).

In relation to the mesoregion, the Recife Metropolitan Region was the only one that showed a significant decrease in the number of rape cases against women during the pandemic. On May 16, 2020, the municipalities of Recife, Olinda, Camaragibe, São Lourenço da Mata, and Jaboatão dos Guararapes implemented a 15-day lockdown. Furthermore, in the state of Pernambuco, there were several decrees suspending activities in cultural facilities, gyms, educational institutions, as well as commerce and non-essential services (Pernambuco, 2020). In fact, during social isolation, victims of violence, being trapped in already violent homes and without contact with other people, were placed in situations that made it difficult to search for help and support.

Figure 2 – Spatial distribution of rape rates per 100,000 women. (a) Pre-pandemic period (b) Pandemic period, Pernambuco, 2018-2021.

Note: Discretization performed using the quartile method

Note that even before the COVID-19 pandemic, women hesitated to report sexual violence for several reasons, including public exposure and family shame (John et al., 2021). Another issue is the trivialization of this violence by the population and the fear of reporting the aggressor (Aslan et al., 2019), in addition to the inequality between men and women imposed by society, cultural and religious values that give men greater decision-making power, thereby making women vulnerable (Fiorotti; Pedroso; Leite, 2020).

The VIDA (VIolência Doméstica, “Domestic Violence”) study on violence against women conducted in Brazil was used to test the permanence of families at home during social isolation. One of its results indicated that the most populous and wealthiest regions have proportionally fewer attacks on women than capitals and regions with smaller total populations. This result demonstrates the need for infrastructure and equipment to implement actions for prevention and protection against violence as important factors in reducing aggression against women (Madeira; Furtado; Dill, 2021). The unequal distribution of security services, such as police stations and shelters, hinders the fight against violence among other regions and municipalities (Cerqueira et al., 2015).

This study has some limitations. Firstly, it included data on women victims of rape registered by the Pernambuco State Secretariat of Social Defense, which does not guarantee that all cases were reported.

Finally, the reductions in the rape rate against women found may reflect underreporting during the pandemic, in addition to stigma, fear, shame, and victim-blaming. For these women, it is necessary to strengthen support networks and mental health programs. In addition, it is important to reinforce the State’s role in protecting women, providing legal support and offering welfare policies.

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